

The Influence of Competency on Performance in Regional Equipment of North Sumatra Province

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Abstract

The purpose of this research is to determine and analyze the influence of competency on employee performance in North Sumatra Human Resources Development Agency employees. This research was carried out at the North Sumatra Human Resources Development Agency. The type of research is associative quantitative. The sample in this study was 107 employees of the North Sumatra Human Resources Development Agency. The sampling technique in this research uses saturated samples so that the entire population will be a sample of 107 people. The research results show that Competency has a significant influence on Employee Performance as shown by the T-Statistic value of $3.826 > 1.659$ and the P Value of $0.000 < 0.05$. This shows that improvements in competency will be able to contribute to improving employee performance at the North Sumatra Human Resources Development Agency.

Keywords: competence; performance; regional equipment.

INTRODUCTION

Human resources have a big role in the company, especially to achieve company goals, therefore companies are required to be able to manage their human resources, because human resources are a valuable company asset for planning, implementing and controlling various operational activities in the company. To maintain the quality of human resource development, companies usually provide training and feedback that can improve employee performance.

Good employee performance is something that organizations desire. The more disciplined employees in a company, the greater the company's overall performance or productivity will increase (Juliyanti & Onsardi, 2020). Employee performance is an important factor in an organization because with good performance an organization is on its way to success. High employee performance will help the organization achieve strategic goals. According to Siagian in (Riyani, 2021), employee performance is influenced by several factors, namely competency, employee training, work environment, work culture, leadership, motivation, discipline and job satisfaction. Meanwhile, the factors that influence performance are motivation, job satisfaction, stress levels, work conditions, compensation system, and job design (Handoko, 2014).

The phenomenon that occurs at the North Sumatra Human Resources Development Agency (BPSDM) shows a decline in performance as reflected in the achievement of Key Performance Indicators (KPI) which is still below the target. The achievement of the KPI in question is the achievement of the capacity to resolve work problems that have not reached the target even though regular maintenance has been carried out on the equipment. Achievement is still 90% of the target set. It is suspected that this decline in performance is related to the inadequate competence of personnel with increasingly high-performance

demands, plus training programs that are not yet on target and reduced employee motivation due to adjustments to welfare components.

To find out the causes of declining employee performance, an internal assessment was carried out within the scope of BPSDM North Sumatra. As a pilot project, an assessment was carried out at the team head (supervisor) level as the person responsible for direct operations in the field and the Central Control Room (CCR) and the results were not satisfactory because they were still below 70% who met the competency requirements. Competency is the ability to carry out or perform a job or task that is based on skills and knowledge and supported by the work attitudes required by the job (Wibowo et al., 2019).

The results of previous research stated otherwise that competence did not have a significant effect on performance (Darmawan et al., 2020). Competent employees are generally able to carry out tasks well and satisfactorily and can be trusted for certain tasks that require a high level of competence. Apart from employee competency, education and training are efforts made to increase organizational productivity, effectiveness and efficiency. This education and training can be provided periodically so that each employee can continue to improve their competence which can improve organizational performance (Erman, 2020).

Employee competency is a distinguishing character that an employee has from other employees. Competency shows skills and knowledge that are characterized by professionalism in supporting work. Competency is an ability based on skills and knowledge which is supported by work attitudes in carrying out their duties in accordance with previously determined job requirements (Sutrisno, 2017). The competencies possessed by employees are able to increase employee commitment to continue working according to their expertise.

Competency is the ability to carry out or perform a job or task that is based on skills and knowledge and supported by the work attitudes required by the job (Wibowo, 2016). Employee competency is a very important thing to pay attention to because it is related to knowledge, skills and work attitudes that are in accordance with established standards (Sutrisno, 2017). For this reason, employees need to improve their quality and abilities by participating in various trainings in order to gain knowledge and insight so they can carry out their duties and responsibilities in carrying out their work.

Competency variable indicators according to Gordon's theory in (Sutrisno, 2017) state that employee competency indicators consist of:

- 1) Knowledge (Knowledge)
- 2) Understanding (Understanding)
- 3) Abilities/Skills (Skills)
- 4) Value (Value)
- 5) Attitude (Attitude)
- 6) Interests

According to (Sutrisno, 2017) Performance is the result of a process that is referred to and measured over a certain period of time based on previously established provisions or agreements. Meanwhile, according to (Mangkunegara, 2016) employee performance is the

achievement of employee work results based on quality and quantity as work performance within a certain period of time which is adjusted to the duties and responsibilities of a group within the organization in carrying out basic tasks and functions that are guided by norms, standard operating procedures, criteria and measures that have been established or are applicable in the organization.

To measure the level of employee performance in this research the author refers to theory (Fahmi, 2017), namely:

- 1) Quality, namely the level of errors, damage, accuracy.
- 2) Quantity, namely the number of jobs produced.
- 3) Use of time at work, namely the level of absenteeism, tardiness, effective working time/lost working hours.
- 4) Cooperate with other people at work.

The aim of this research is to analyze and determine the influence of competency on performance in regional apparatus of North Sumatra Province. The concept of this research is as depicted in the following conceptual framework image:

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

METHOD

This type of research is casual associative quantitative research. This research was carried out at the North Sumatra Human Resources Development Agency. The time this research was carried out was from March to April 2024. According to (Sugiyono, 2018) population is a generalization area consisting of objects/subjects that have certain qualities and characteristics determined by the researcher to be studied and then conclusions drawn. In this study, the population used was the entire number of employees at the North Sumatra Human Resources Development Agency, totaling 107 people.

The sampling technique used in this research was a saturated sample. According to (Sugiyono, 2018b) Saturated sampling is a sample selection technique if all members of the population are sampled, where the entire population in this study is sampled, namely 107 employees.

The data that will be used from this research is the data from the questionnaire distributed to respondents consisting of all employees in all divisions. The data analysis technique used in this research is a quantitative data analysis method using SPSS version 25.0.

Validity and reliability tests were carried out in order to test the quality of the research data. The validity test decision making criteria are as follows: If $r_{count} > r_{table}$, then the question item is valid. If $r_{count} < r_{table}$, then the question item is invalid.

Meanwhile, the reliability test criteria are formulated if $r\text{-alpha} > r\text{-table}$ then the statement is reliable and if $r\text{-alpha} < r\text{-table}$ then the statement is not reliable.

The linear regression model was formulated in this research with the following formula:

$$Y = a + bX$$

Where :

Y = Employee Performance

X = Competence

a = Constant

b = Regression coefficient

The t-test in this research was carried out to determine the significance of the influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable (Kuncoro & Hardani, 2013). According to (Kuncoro & Hardani, 2013) the determination test (R^2) is used to measure how much influence the independent variable has on the dependent variable. In other words, the coefficient of determination is used to assess the magnitude of the influence of the independent variable studied, namely Competence (X), on the dependent variable, namely employee performance (Y). The coefficient of determination (R^2) value ranges from zero to one ($0 < R^2 < 1$) which means, if $R^2 = 0$, then there is no influence between variable (X) and variable (Y). Conversely, if R^2 approaches 1, then the influence between variable (X) and variable (Y) becomes stronger. This coefficient of determination test was carried out using SPSS version 25.0 software.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Contents Results and Discussion

1. Research result

a) Descriptive Analysis

Descriptive Analysis This test is used to determine the minimum and maximum scores, the highest scores, rating scores and standard deviations for each variable. The results are as follows:

Table 2. Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Competence	107	1.83	5.00	3.8493	,82098
Performance	107	2.00	5.00	4.2243	,75230
Valid N (listwise)	107				

The table above shows that the measurement results show that respondents assess the competency and performance of employees at the North Sumatra Human Resources Development Agency as above average, with mean values of 3,849 and 4,224 respectively on a scale of 1-5. The variation in respondents' assessments of these two variables is quite moderate, with almost the same standard deviation (0.8209 for competency and 0.7523 for

employee performance), indicating that although there are individual differences in perception, the majority of respondents have a fairly positive view of both variables. the.

b) Validity and Reliability Test Results

Validity Test Results

The validity test is used to measure whether a questionnaire is valid or not. Validity testing carried out in this research was through the Corrected Item-Total Correlation test or better known as Person Correlation.

Table 3. Competency Variable Validity Test Results (X)

Variable	Correlation Value	Probability	Information
KOM1	0.638 > 0.190	0.000 < 0.05	Valid
KOM2	0.687 > 0.190	0.000 < 0.05	Valid
KOM3	0.714 > 0.190	0.000 < 0.05	Valid
KOM4	0.619 > 0.190	0.000 < 0.05	Valid
KOM5	0.720 > 0.190	0.000 < 0.05	Valid
KOM6	0.680 > 0.190	0.000 < 0.05	Valid

Source: Processed with SPSS version 25

From the data above, it can be stated that the indicators for the Competency variable have a correlation coefficient value of > 0.190 with a significance value of $0.000 < 0.05$, so it can be concluded that the indicators for the Competency variable are valid (Sugiyono, 2018a).

Table 4. Validity Test Results for Employee Performance Variables (Y)

Variable	Correlation Value	Probability	Information
KIN1	0.801 > 0.190	0.000 < 0.05	Valid
KIN2	0.792 > 0.190	0.000 < 0.05	Valid
KIN3	0.694 > 0.190	0.000 < 0.05	Valid
KIN4	0.742 > 0.190	0.000 < 0.05	Valid

Source: Processed with SPSS version 25

From the data above it can be stated that all indicators on employee performance variables have a correlation coefficient value greater than 0.190 with a significance value of $0.000 < 0.05$ so it can be concluded that the statements for employee performance variables are valid, (Sugiyono, 2018a).

Reliability Test Results

According to (Ghozali, 2018) the reliability test aims to measure how reliable or reliable the questionnaire distributed to respondents is, which is useful as an instrument in this research. The reliability measurement method used in this research is by looking at the Cronbach Alpha (a) value. The questionnaire is declared reliable if the Cronbach Alpha (a) value is > 0.61 .

Table 5. Reliability Test Results

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
Competence	0.760	6
Employee Performance	0.753	4

Source: Processed with SPSS version 25.0

Based on table 5, it is known that the Cronbach Alpa (a) value of the employee competency and performance variables is greater than 0.60. So it can be concluded that all indicators in the variable instrument are declared reliable or reliable so that they can proceed to research hypothesis testing

c) Quantitative Analysis

This analysis is intended to determine the influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable. The test results are as follows:

Simple Linear Regression Analysis

This regression test is intended to determine changes in the dependent variable if the independent variable experiences changes. The test results are as follows:

Table 6. Simple Linear Regression Test Results

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	2,990	,330		9,071	,000
	Competence	,321	,084	,350	3,826	,000

a. Dependent Variable: Performance

Based on the test results in table 8, the regression equation $Y = 2.990 + 0.321X$ is obtained. This equation is explained as follows: 1) A constant of 2.990 means that if there is no competency, then there is an employee performance of 2.990 points. The competency regression coefficient is 0.321, meaning that competency influences an increase in employee performance by 0.321 for every 1 point increase.

Analysis of the Coefficient of Determination

To determine the magnitude of the influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable, a coefficient of determination analysis was carried out. The test results are as follows:

Table 7. Coefficient of Determination Test Results

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	,350a	,122	,114	,70813

a. Predictors: (Constant), Competence

The test results in table 7 show an Adjusted R Square value of 0.114 or 11.40%, which means that competency has a low influence on employee performance, while the remaining 88.60% is influenced by other factors that have not been studied.

t Test Results (Hypothesis Test)

Hypothesis testing with the t test is used to determine whether or not there is an influence of the dependent variable on the independent variable with the following hypothesis formulation:

Ho: There is no influence of competency on employee performance at the North Sumatra Human Resources Development Agency

Ha: There is an influence of competency on employee performance at the North Sumatra Human Resources Development Agency

The following are the results of the hypothesis test as shown in the following table:

Table 8. Hypothesis Test Results

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	2,990	,330	9,071	,000
	Competence	,321	,084	,350	,000

a. Dependent Variable: Performance

Based on the test results in table 8, the calculated t value is 3.826 > t table 1.659, with a significance value of 0.000 < 0.05, thus it can be stated that Ho is rejected and Ha is accepted or that there is a positive and significant influence between competency on employee performance at the Resource Development Agency. Man of North Sumatra.

Contents of Discussion Results

The findings in this research can be strengthened by referring to relevant previous research findings. In the context of the influence of competency on employee performance at the North Sumatra Human Resources Development Agency, this research shows results that are in line with the theory put forward by Abdi and Wahid (2018) which explains that if employees have high competency, they will be able to improve the employee's own performance. . Improving work competency needs to be done within the company organization. Employees who have work competence tend to have good abilities in carrying out work and have the skills to be able to complete work based on the work targets given by their place of work. This can provide work enthusiasm within employees to continue to progress in carrying out work which can improve performance within the company. Meanwhile, if employees do not have high competence, they tend not to have the ability to work. Where employees do not fully have the skills to complete the work, resulting in poor performance within the company. Even though employees have knowledge about work, but it is not balanced with the skills they have, it will be difficult

for the work to achieve the specified work targets so that the results achieved will be less than optimal.

CLOSING

Conclusion

From the results of data analysis resulting from the research and discussion described above, it can be concluded that Competence has a positive and significant influence on the Performance of Employees of the North Sumatra Human Resources Development Agency with a calculated t value of $3.826 > t$ table 1.659 , with a significance value of $0.000 < 0,05$. These results indicate that if competency is increased, employee performance is likely not to increase.

The adjusted R Square value is 0.114 or 11.40% , which means that competency has a low influence on employee performance, while the remaining 88.60% is influenced by other factors that have not been studied. Overall, this research provides insight into the importance of factors such as competency in influencing employee performance at the North Sumatra Human Resources Development Agency.

Suggestions and Acknowledgments

Based on the results of the research, discussion and conclusions obtained, suggestions that can be given are that the competency and skills variables need attention. Therefore, the leadership of the North Sumatra Human Resources Development Agency should improve the skills and knowledge of employees, for example employees with a D3 education level can immediately take a Bachelor's degree. Employees with insufficient knowledge and skills can improve their knowledge and skills by attending training both internally and externally held by the North Sumatra Human Resources Development Agency. It is hoped that these steps can further improve employee competency so that employee performance can be improved.

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